

Compounds of Dimethylglyoxime with Cobaltous Chloride.

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Feigl and Rubinstein (*Annalen*, 1923, **433**, 183) have described the preparation of a dark olive-green compound in acetone solution from crystalline cobaltous chloride and dimethylglyoxime. As the substance does not respond to any usual tests for Co^{++} , such as by sulphuretted hydrogen, caustic potash, rubeanic acid, etc., nor for the dimethylglyoxime, such as by the addition of nickel salts, they assume that the compound is a strong cobaltous complex of formula $[\text{DH}_2 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{DH}_2] \text{Cl}_2$

where $\text{DH}_2 = \begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C} = \text{NOH} \\ | \\ \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C} = \text{NOH} \end{array}$, with a co-ordination number four for

cobalt. Thilo and Heilborn (*Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 1441), starting from anhydrous cobaltous chloride and dimethylglyoxime in acetone solution, have prepared a deep red crystalline substance having the same composition as that of the green compound described by Feigl. The red compound is very unstable and passes readily in solution (in acetone), specially in the presence of a trace of water, into the stable green modification. The chlorine atoms in both the compounds are precipitated by silver nitrate.

The constitution of these compounds have been discussed by Thilo and his co-workers (Thilo and Friedrich, *Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 2990; Thilo and Heilborn, *loc. cit.*). According to them, it is the red compound which should be represented by the above constitution $[\text{DH}_2 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{DH}_2] \text{Cl}_2$.

To the green compound they attribute the constitution for the following reason. The central cobalt atom is here hexa-coordinated with non-ionic chlorine atoms. Feigl and Rubinstein (*loc. cit.*) have already mentioned that the green compound hydrolyses in aqueous solution which, therefore, reacts acid, the compound dissolving with a brown colour. Thilo and Heilborn (*loc. cit.*) assume that this is not a case of ordinary hydrolysis, but the substitution

of chlorine atom in the complex by the OH group of water leading to the formation of hydroxy compounds and HCl, which then reacts with AgNO₃.

This is also supported by Feigl and Rubinstein's (*loc. cit.*) isolation of the compound (DH₂)₂·Co·(OH)Br. Hieber and Leutert (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 2296,) have also shown that the green compound in acetone solution is a non-electrolyte. That the chlorine atoms are in the *trans*-position, is inferred by Thilo from the behaviour of the corresponding bromide towards ethylenediamine (*cf.* Feigl and Rubinstein, *loc. cit.*), as the Br atoms are not replaced by a single bidentate group like ethylenediamine.

With a view to throw more light upon the constitution of these interesting and much discussed compounds, a further study of their properties was undertaken, the results of which are embodied in the present paper.

It might be recalled here that instances of strong cobaltous complexes of the highly stable type, as represented by the above green salt, are extremely rare. Among the known strong cobaltous complexes, mention can be made only of potassium cobaltocyanide which is very unstable, and of cobalt biguanide and cobalt rubeanate, which are highly insoluble.

It is well known that the magnetic susceptibility of a paramagnetic ion usually undergoes a profound alteration, when the latter forms the central atom of a perfect complex. It has been further established that all complex cobaltic compounds are diamagnetic, though Co⁺⁺ or Co⁺⁺⁺ are strongly paramagnetic, having magnetic moments of about 24 and 14 Weiss's magnetons respectively. All cobaltous complexes so far examined, excepting the three just mentioned above, exhibit the same susceptibility value as the Co⁺⁺ in the simple salts. Of the above mentioned three compounds, only potassium cobaltocyanide is diamagnetic, cobalt biguanide and cobalt rubeanate, each shows a susceptibility value of 10 Weiss's magnetons approximately. The case of these compounds has previously been discussed (Rây, *Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1932, p. 141, *Presidential*

Address, Chem. Sec.; Rây and Bhar, J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1928, 5, 497). Magnetic susceptibility is thus found to be a more or less unfailing guide in determining the complex character, as well as the valency, of the central paramagnetic ion. In the case of Feigl's green compound the susceptibility measurement showed that the compound is diamagnetic. This fact, taken together with the characteristic properties of the substance, such as its solubility, hydrolysis, etc., strongly suggests that in this compound the central cobalt atom is in the trivalent stage. In other words, the salt represents a cobaltic complex. It has also been possible to isolate the first product of its hydrolysis. This latter, which has the composition $[\text{DH}_2 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{DH}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}]$ and resembles the corresponding bromide already described by Feigl, is also diamagnetic, showing that the valency of the central Co atom remains unchanged during the hydrolysis. The green salt also slowly liberates iodine from KI solution, indicating a higher stage of valency for the cobalt atom. It has been further observed that when a solution of cobaltous salt is mixed with one of dimethylglyoxime in alcohol, the colour of the cobalt salt changes, and the mixture slowly liberates iodine from acidified KI solution.

The hydrolysis of the salt has been further studied in aqueous solution. It is an established fact of complex chemistry that unstable weak acidic or basic ions are stabilised or strengthened by complex formation. When CoCl_2 does not appreciably hydrolyse, there is no reason why it should do so to such a marked extent after combination with dimethylglyoxime. For, it has been found that the hydrolysis in aqueous solution is complete. Hence the Cl atoms, as has already been pointed out by Thilo, Hieber and Leutert (*loc. cit.*) are inside the complex zone; the central Co atom must, therefore, be in a higher state of oxidation.

From the considerations set forth above, it can be concluded that Feigl's green salt is not a tetra-co-ordinated cobaltous complex as suggested by him, nor is it a hexa-co-ordinated cobaltous complex as assumed by Thilo and his co-workers. This naturally applies to all the other so-called cobaltous complexes, related to this green salt, described by Feigl and Rubinstein (*loc. cit.*) and also to the compound described by Dübsky and Brychta (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1929, II, 549).

The constitution of the green compound should, therefore, be represented by the formula in which one of the hydrogen atoms of one dimethylglyoxime molecule is replaced by the cobalt atom:

The green colour of the salt, as well as its reaction with ethylenediamine (Thilo, *loc. cit.*), indicates that it is a *trans*-dichloro compound.

The oxidation of cobaltous atom into cobaltic stage occurs evidently in a spontaneous way during its reaction with dimethylglyoxime. Such instances of spontaneous oxidation during complex formation are not rare in the case of Co atom (*cf.* Rây, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 208, 393; Rây and Chackrabarty, *ibid.*, 1933, 211, 176).

On the other hand, Thilo's red isomer gives a susceptibility value of 19.04 Weiss's magnetons, a value which a Co^{++} should theoretically possess according to Bose-Stoner's view. Ordinary simple cobaltous salts, solid or in solution (*e. g.* CoSO_4 , CoCl_2 , etc.), give, however, a susceptibility value of 24—25 Weiss's magnetons. In a fourfold co-ordination compound this value has been found to be reduced somewhat—the lowest value found is 20.9 for $[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2]\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Rây and Bhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 499). Similar behaviour has also been observed in the case of nickel compounds as well. This discrepancy from the theoretical value has been attributed by Bose and Stoner to imperfect neutralisation of the orbital moments of the electrons by the field of neighbouring molecules and ions. In the present case of Thilo's red isomer, the orbital moments of the outer electrons of the Co atom appear, therefore, to be completely neutralised. The green and the red isomers are, therefore, sharply distinguished by their magnetic properties. The valence condition of the central Co atom is thus proved to be different in the two complexes, Feigl's green compound having the central Co atom in the tervalent stage, whereas Thilo's red isomer contains a bivalent cobalt. The properties of red isomer also lead to the same conclusion as has already been pointed out by Thilo and Heilborn (*loc. cit.*).

We have also tried to prepare Dübsky and Brychta's black compound of the alleged composition and constitution $[\text{DH}_2 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{DH}]\text{Cl}$ (*loc. cit.*). Though a black crystalline compound, as described by them, has been obtained, its composition, however, does

not agree with the above formula. The analytical results correspond approximately to the formula $[2 \text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{DH}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. The substance was found to be feebly magnetic. This suggests that it is an impure mixture of the green compound and its products of hydrolysis. The properties of the black crystals also resemble those of the green compound.

It is now clear that the green compound and its red isomer should be represented by the following constitutional formulæ.

Hexa-co-ordinated
tervalent cobalt.
Diamagnetic.

Tetra-co-ordinated
bivalent cobalt.
Strongly paramagnetic.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Feigl's Green Salt.

The compound was prepared, as described by Feigl and Rubinstein (*loc. cit.*), from $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and dimethylglyoxime in acetone solution. (Found: Cl, 19.62; Co, 16.35. Calc., Cl, 19.60; Co, 16.30 per cent). The aqueous solution of the substance is strongly acid, liberates iodine slowly from acidified KI solution and evolves hydrogen with metallic zinc.

The magnetic susceptibility of the dry solid at $30^\circ = \chi_m \times 10^6 = -0.281$.

Molecular conductivity in aqueous solution at 18° .

v (dilution in litres)...	32	64	128	256	512	1024
M_v	...	335.7	354.1	362.2	374.6	...
						388.7

The molecular conductivity of HCl at infinite dilution is about 381. This clearly indicates that the hydrolysis is complete in the sense of the equation:

and that the product of hydrolysis in presence of the liberated HCl is a non-electrolyte, the conductivity of the solution being equal to that of HCl only.

Chloro-hydroxo-dimethylglyoxime Cobalt.

When a saturated solution of the green salt was strongly cooled, a silky yellowish brown crystalline substance gradually separated.

This was washed with cold water and dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid. {Found: N, 16.51; Cl, 10.44; Co, 17.16. $[\text{DH}_2 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{DH}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}]$ requires N, 16.35; Cl, 10.37; Co, 17.13 per cent}. Magnetic susceptibility at $30^\circ = \chi_m \times 10^6 = -0.053$.

The substance is sparingly soluble in water, giving a brown solution, which also reacts acid due to further hydrolysis.

The constitution of this brown compound should be represented, similarly to that of the green salt, as follows:

When the green compound was treated with aqueous ammonia, a yellow crystalline substance was obtained, containing both ammonia and chlorine. The aqueous solution of this compound also liberates iodine from acidified KI solution.

Thilo's Red Isomer.

This substance was prepared, as described by Thilo and Heilborn, from anhydrous CoCl_2 and dimethylglyoxime in dry acetone solution. The anhydrous cobalt chloride was prepared according to Baxter and Dorcas (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 362) by heating $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in a current of dry HCl and N_2 to 300° . (Found: Cl, 20.11; Co, 16.42. Calc., Cl, 19.60; Co, 16.30 per cent). Magnetic susceptibility at $34^\circ = \chi_m \times 10^6 = 16.53$, η_{weis} = 19.04 (corr.).

Dübsky's Black Compound.

The substance was prepared according to Dübsky and Brychta's method as abstracted in the *Centralblatt* (*loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 12.2; Cl, 20.16; Co, 17.64. $2\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{DH}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 12.69; Cl, 21.43; Co, 17.82, per cent).

It gave a susceptibility value of $\chi_m \times 10^6 = 0.9557$ at 34° , $\eta_{\text{weis}} = 4.40$. The composition of the compound is not quite clear, and it appears to be contaminated with some decomposition product.